

Stellar radial migration in galactic discs

Anaëlle Hallé¹, P. Di Matteo², M. Haywood², F. Combes³

1. Max Planck Institute for Astrophysics, Germany. 2. GEPI and 3. LERMA, France

Abstract

Radial migration in galactic discs has been more and more studied because of puzzling observations in the Milky Way or local galaxies. Numerical simulations show the migration depends on the parameters of non-axisymmetric patterns (bars or spiral arms). In particular, radial migration may not always be able to cause some observational features of the outer parts of discs. Its impact on the thickness of discs is also debated. We present some results of numerical simulations of isolated galactic discs. Radial migration is studied with respect to the location of the main resonances of the bar of these bar-dominated discs.

Observations motivating the study of radial migration

Main paradigm for a long time in evolution models of galactic discs: stars staying on nearly circular orbits at their birth guiding radius + discs forming inside-out.

But some observations difficult to explain:

Age-metallicity relation scatter in the solar neighbourhood in the Milky Way.

U-shaped age profiles in nearby galaxies Bakos et al 2008, Yoachim et al 2012, Laura-Ruiz et al 2016, e.g.. Older stars present in the outskirts of discs that are supposed to form last.

Is radial migration responsible?

Sources of radial migration

Radial migration (change of galactocentric radius) can be caused by:

- scattering (e.g. by molecular clouds)
- interaction with other galaxies (mergers)
- radial oscillations possibly increasing: **blurring**
- exchange of angular momentum with disc resonances: **churning** by resonant patterns (bar or spiral arms) Sellwood & Binney (2002): transient spiral arms can cause efficient churning.

Typical orbit in an axisymmetric or mildly non-axisymmetric potential. Green: guiding radius

Example of an isolated Sb type galaxy simulated with a N-body code (Gadget-2). Main non-axisymmetric pattern: bar. Churning occurs mainly around the corotation (CR) of the bar during the whole simulated time (see Halle et al 2015).

Variation of galactocentric radius between two times. Effect of blurring + churning.

Variation of guiding radius. Effect of churning.

Determination of the positions of corotation and some Lindblad resonances

Is churning efficient at mixing discs?

Change of the bar speed (e.g. due to angular momentum exchange with the bulge of dark-matter halo) implies a shift of the location of corotation. A large part of the disc can thus be affected by churning.

Stars can be churned outwards and inwards periodically due to the permanence of the bar. But some stars truly churned outwards even when averaged on long periods of time because they are trapped at the bar corotation of growing radius..

Impact of churning of a bar on the outer parts of discs strongly depends on the relative location of the corotation radius of the bar with respect to the disc size.

In grey scale: stars trapped at the corotation of the bar.

If "inner" and "outer" discs of a galaxy have different origins, churning may not be able to mix them efficiently and they may keep strong differences in metallicity or enrichment

Metallicity step persisting during a number of Gyrs. Colours in transparency: location of the ILR (blue), CR (red) and OLR (green).

Disc thickening and radial migration in thick discs

Radial migration and disc thickening: debated question. Declining vertical velocity dispersion with radius -> outwards migrators from dynamically hotter regions should heat the outer parts of discs.

But: `provenance bias` (Vera-Ciro et al 2014, 2016): stars the most sensitive to mostly planar non-axisymmetries: group of stars with small velocity dispersion compared to local velocity dispersion.

However: importance of bias seems to depend on the nature of the non-axisymmetry: the bias might be weaker for bars, especially when they thicken, than for vertically thin spiral arms. See Halle, Di Matteo and Haywood 2017 (in preparation).

Change in radius of thin and thick disc components.

Change in guiding radius of thin and thick disc components.

On-going work/perspectives

With Guinevere Kauffmann (MPA): including gas and stellar flows due to radial migration in semi-analytic models of disc galaxies evolution (Fu et al 2010, 2012, 2013, Wang et al 2012, Luo et al 2016).